

PROSPECTS FOR THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE FORMATION OF PUBLIC HEALTH: YESTERDAY AND TODAY

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Relevance. Public health is characterized by the preservation and improvement of the population's health as a whole. It studies how socioeconomic factors, the environment, and lifestyle influence human well-being. This highlights the need to optimize the field through the implementation of the most advanced achievements of science and technology, including artificial intelligence (AI) technologies.

The aim of the study is to determine the significance and prospects of applying AI technologies in the formation of public health.

The material of the study includes opinions and conclusions of specialized centers and institutions regarding the use of AI technologies in diagnostics and preventive and therapeutic measures for a wide range of diseases and pathological conditions.

The method of research is the analysis of issues related to assessing the effectiveness of digital technologies in processing medical examination data on the studied problems.

The results of the studies have shown that, at present, significant attention is paid to AI in the early diagnosis, therapeutic and preventive technologies, and even rehabilitation of a large number of pathologies, such as in oncohematology, oncology, radiology, cardiovascular diseases, neurological disorders, and hematological system diseases (Kulbakin D.E. et al., 2022; Ganichev P.A. et al., 2022).

1. A certain importance has been identified in the use of AI for analyzing issues of intensive care and resuscitation, as well as in telemedicine, dentistry, traumatology, orthopedics, and surgery of various organs and systems (Bril E.V. et al., 2023; Shanina A.Yu., 2023).
2. A significant role of AI technologies has also been established in the interpretation of patients' anamnesis, objective clinical examinations, laboratory, and visual-instrumental studies (ultrasound, CT, MRI) in determining the final diagnosis of major diseases of the nervous and cardiovascular systems (Vasiliev Yu.A. et al., 2024; Mamedov M.N. et al., 2024).
3. Recently, considerable attention has been given to the role of AI technologies in determining the compatibility of family life among individuals with kinship relations (Kudryavtseva E.V. et al., 2024).
4. There are also reports highlighting the importance of AI technologies in socioeconomic relations, educational processes of secondary and higher levels, and international cooperation (Yagudina A.R. et al., 2022).

Conclusion. Thus, the presented analysis of AI technology applications demonstrates the significant role of digital innovations across a wide spectrum of medicine, education, and public administration. The effectiveness of AI in these areas of social life confirms the necessity of expanding the use of digital technologies to address urgent issues of healthcare in general, and public health in particular.